

PROFESSIONAL TRAINING AND SCHOOL SUPPORT AS PREDICTORS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MATATAG CURRICULUM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18531009>

ABSTRACT

This study is quantitative-correlational and explores the relationships among professional training, school support, and the success of implementing the MATATAG curriculum. The study is conducted in the following schools: Little Baguio National High School, Halapitan National High School, and Sacramento Valley Integrated School, which serve as the study locale. Moreover, this study used three standardized questionnaires. Results revealed that Professional training across six domains yields an overall mean of 3.97 (SD = 0.19), interpreted as often. Meanwhile, school support yields an overall mean of 2.67 (SD = 0.21), which is interpreted as rarely. Lastly, the success of the MATATAG Curriculum's implementation yields an overall mean score of 4.06 (SD = 0.19), which is often interpreted as indicating success. Inferentially, professional training is associated with curriculum implementation in certain domains. Also, none of the domains of school support were significantly correlated with the success of the MATATAG Curriculum implementation. Based on the study's results, to ensure the effective implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum, stakeholders must invest in ongoing, targeted professional training that promotes inclusive and reflective teaching practices. Since school support showed limited impact, reforms should emphasize trust-building, mentorship, and shared leadership rather than relying solely on logistical aid. Empowering teachers through collaborative and developmental strategies is key to sustaining curriculum success across diverse educational contexts.

Keywords: *Professional training, School support, Success of the MATATAG Curriculum, Quantitative, Education, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Successful curricula lead to high student performance, improved literacy, numeracy, and life skills. Data-driven evaluations help assess whether students have achieved the expected competencies. In the Philippines, the Department of Education envisions the MATATAG Curriculum to produce lifelong, peace-loving Filipino learners who embody the core values of Maka-Diyos (God-fearing), Makatao (People-centered), Makalikasan (Nature-loving), and Makabansa (Nationalistic). Moreover, numerous variables influence the success of a curriculum, yet the correlation between professional teacher training and school support is significant. To note, when teachers are well-trained and backed by a supportive school system, curriculum implementation becomes more effective, leading to better student performance and overall educational success.

Globally, curriculum implementation faces several challenges that affect the quality and effectiveness of education. Many countries, such as Australia, struggle to ensure that teachers receive sufficient professional development to effectively implement new curricula (Ferguson-Patrick et al., 2018). Without proper training, educators may struggle to deliver lessons efficiently and align teaching methods with curriculum goals. Some regions, even in the United States, face challenges in achieving curriculum success due to limited access to updated textbooks, technology, and learning materials, making it difficult for schools to implement modern curricula (Campbell-Phillips, 2023) fully. Poor infrastructure, such as overcrowded classrooms and limited digital access, further hampers education. Some curricula in Brazil fail to address 21st-century skills, local employment demands, or cultural relevance, leaving students unprepared for the modern workforce and global challenges (Costin & Pontual, 2020). A rigid, outdated curriculum does not keep pace with evolving societal and technological advancements.

In the ASEAN region, countries have different curricula, making regional integration difficult. In Indonesia, standardizing education while respecting cultural diversity remains a challenge (Alam, 2020). Moreover, disparities in education quality, teacher training, and resources exist between developed and developing ASEAN nations. Countries like Vietnam struggle with outdated curricula that do not align with modern workforce demands (Pham et al., 2020). Some curricula do not fully prepare students for international competitiveness, leading to gaps in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics education, Vocational training, and Language proficiency. Lastly, as reported in Myanmar, even when curriculum reforms are introduced, teacher preparedness, funding, and policy inconsistencies hinder effective implementation (Arphattananon, 2021).

The Philippines is no different; it faces several challenges in curriculum implementation, which affect educational quality and student learning outcomes. Many educators struggle with adapting to curriculum changes due to insufficient training and professional development. This affects their ability to deliver lessons effectively (Diquito, 2024). To note, the MATATAG Curriculum has faced criticism from educators and stakeholders, highlighting several implementation challenges. First, the curriculum reportedly increases the teaching load by 30%, requiring teachers to handle more subjects and students, which

has led to concerns about burnout (Estrellado, 2023). Second, some schools may have longer school hours, with classes lasting until 8 PM or later, raising concerns about student well-being and safety (Kilag, 2024). Third, critics argue that the curriculum was implemented without adequate consultation with teachers, parents, and students, making it less responsive to actual classroom needs (Herrera, 2025). In the research locale of San Fernando District 1 in the Division of Bukidnon, the same experience has been observed. Note that one of the school heads shared teachers' concerns that the curriculum does not fully address real-world skills or the evolving needs of Filipino students, potentially repeating past issues with the K to 12 programs. Aside from it, issues such as funding limitations, resource shortages, and policy inconsistencies may hinder the smooth rollout of the curriculum. It poses a problem not only at the administrative level, but also cascades to teachers and, worst of all, to students.

Given this existing problem, the researcher felt compelled to conduct this study in the research locale, focusing on secondary education. The researcher plans to pursue this, as most of the problems stem from the elementary department, which does not even emphasize the secondary level. Notably, many secondary schools lack adequate learning materials, technology, and classroom space, making it challenging to fully implement the curriculum (Kilag et al., 2024). Since the researcher is eager to study the dependent variable, namely the success of the MATATAG curriculum, the researcher seeks the pertinent variables that may correlate with its success. The body of knowledge in educational research indicates that professional training and school support are essential for successful curriculum implementation, as they equip teachers with the skills, knowledge, and confidence to deliver lessons effectively (Little & Paul, 2020; González-Campos, 2022; Smith & Gillespie, 2023). Moreover, strong school support, including leadership guidance, adequate resources, and educator collaboration, fosters a positive teaching environment that enhances instructional quality (Toropova et al., 2021; Leithwood et al., 2020; Purwanto, 2020). Henceforth, the researcher will conduct a study about professional training and school support as predictors of school success in the implementation of MATATAG curriculum which will be responded by secondary teachers coming from San Fernando District 1 specifically Little Baguio National High School (Little Baguio San Fernando Bukidnon), Sacramento Valley Integrated School (Sacramento Valley San Fernando Bukidnon) and Halapitan National High School (Halapitan San Fernando Bukidnon).

Research Questions

This study explored the relationships among professional training, school support, and the success of implementing the MATATAG curriculum. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of professional training among secondary teachers based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), in terms of?
 - a. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
 - b. Learning Environment
 - c. Diversity of Learner

- d. Curriculum and Planning
 - e. Community Linkage and Professional Engagement
 - f. Personal growth and Professional Development
2. What is the level of school support as perceived by secondary teachers, specifically in terms of administrative support?
 - a. Relational trust
 - b. Mentorship
 - c. Adequate Preparation
 3. What is the level of success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation as observed by secondary teachers in terms of?
 - a. Curriculum Design and Content
 - b. Teaching and Learning Enhancement
 - c. Implementation and Support
 4. Is there a significant relationship between professional training as a predictor of the success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between school support as a predictor of the success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation?

METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative using a descriptive-correlation design. Quantitative research is a systematic investigation that primarily focuses on quantifying relationships, behaviors, or phenomena by collecting and analyzing numerical data (Salinas-Navarro et al., 2022). This type of research employs statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques to explore patterns, test theories, and make predictions. Quantitative research typically involves structured methods such as surveys, experiments, and secondary data analysis, ensuring replicability and reliability of findings. It aims to produce objective, generalizable results through rigorous data collection and analysis, often using tools such as closed-ended questionnaires, standardized tests, or existing datasets.

According to (Gerlich, 2025), quantitative research is characterized by the use of measurable data to formulate facts and uncover patterns, which provide broad, generalizable insights into the research question. This approach is essential in fields such as social sciences, healthcare, and education, where it helps to identify trends, establish relationships, and provide evidence-based conclusions. Moreover, correlational research does not establish causation but rather identifies patterns and associations that can inform further study. Researchers such as (Saro, J. M, et al. 2024) have emphasized the importance of correlational research for understanding complex real-world relationships and developing theories. Contextually, this study explores the relationships among professional training, school support, and the success of implementing the MATATAG curriculum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the level of professional training among secondary teachers based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), in terms of?

- a. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
- b. Learning Environment
- c. Diversity of Learner
- d. Curriculum and Planning
- e. Community Linkage and Professional Engagement
- g. Personal growth and Professional Development

Table 1
Level of Professional Training in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Mean	Std. Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Content knowledge and its application within and across curriculum areas	3.87	.72	Often
2. Research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning.	3.77	.66	Often
3. Positive use of ICT	3.77	.80	Often
4. Strategies for promoting literacy and numeracy	3.66	.72	Often
5. Strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	3.77	.66	Often
6. Mother Tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning	4.08	.89	Often
7. Classroom communication strategies.	3.77	.66	Often
Mean Score	3.82	.42	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

The findings in Table 1 demonstrate that secondary school teachers frequently apply a range of pedagogical competencies, as evidenced by an overall mean score of 3.82 (SD = 0.42), which is interpreted as *often*. Notably, the highest-rated competency pertains to the use of the Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English in teaching and learning (M = 4.08, SD = 0.89), suggesting that linguistic adaptability remains a central strength among teachers. Conversely, strategies for promoting literacy and numeracy (M = 3.66, SD =

0.72) registered the lowest mean, indicating a relative area for improvement. The data imply that while teachers consistently demonstrate adequate content knowledge and instructional adaptability, there are gaps in applying strategies that directly foster foundational literacy and numeracy. This imbalance suggests the need for more targeted training initiatives emphasizing literacy and numeracy interventions, which are fundamental to learner success across disciplines. Moreover, the consistency in scores (means clustering between 3.66 and 4.08) underscores that most teachers perceive themselves as moderately confident but not exceptional in this domain. In line with the Department of Education's professional standards and international teaching benchmarks, continuous capacity-building in content pedagogy remains critical to enhancing teachers' overall instructional effectiveness.

Three recent studies underscore the persistent gap between teachers' instructional adaptability and their practical implementation of foundational literacy and numeracy (FLN) strategies. (Sahoo and Padhi, 2023) emphasize that while educators often possess strong content knowledge, they lack training in developmentally appropriate, play-based, and multisensory pedagogies essential for FLN, especially in early childhood settings aligned with NEP 2020 reforms. (Gupta and Ram, 2025) further highlight that, despite policy-driven initiatives such as the NIPUN Bharat Mission, challenges, including inadequate teacher preparation, limited access to contextualized learning materials, and weak assessment practices, hinder the translation of instructional flexibility into foundational skill acquisition. Complementing this, (Goel, 2022) identifies a learning crisis in mathematics and language at the primary level, attributing it to traditional rote-based methods and insufficient emphasis on competency-based learning. The NEP 2020 seeks to address this through structural reforms and teacher capacity-building.

Table 2
Level of Professional Training in Learning Environment

Learning Environment	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. <i>Learner safety and security.</i>	3.80	.75	Often
2. <i>Fair learning environment</i>	4.17	.84	Often
3. <i>Classroom management</i>	4.30	.66	Always
4. <i>Support for learner participation</i>	4.44	.71	Always
5. <i>Promotion of purposive learning</i>	3.92	.47	Often
6. <i>Management of learner behavior</i>	3.79	.58	Often
<i>Mean Score</i>	4.07	.26	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

As shown in Table 2, teachers reported a generally positive level of professional training in creating and maintaining conducive learning environments, with an overall mean of 4.07 (SD = 0.26), indicating that this was *often the case*. The highest indicator was support for learner participation (M = 4.44, SD = 0.71), reflecting a strong emphasis on inclusivity and student engagement in classroom practices. Classroom management (M = 4.30, SD = 0.66) was also rated highly, highlighting teachers' capacity to maintain structure and order. In contrast, management of learner behavior (M = 3.79, SD = 0.58) scored the lowest, suggesting that while teachers can facilitate participation and fairness, managing behavioral challenges is more nuanced. These findings imply that secondary educators excel at creating supportive, participatory learning environments but may need additional professional development in behavior management. Such training would further balance the strengths observed in classroom climate with consistent approaches to discipline, thereby promoting equity and holistic learner development.

Table 3
Level of Professional Training in Diversity Learning

Diversity of Learners	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Addressing learners' gender, needs, strengths, and interests	4.18	.78	Often
2. Consideration of linguistic, cultural, and socio-economic backgrounds	4.18	.76	Often
3. Support for learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents	4.61	.71	Always
4. Assistance for learners in difficult circumstances	3.63	.62	Often
5. Inclusion of indigenous learners	3.41	.52	Often
Mean Score	4.00	.32	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 3 reveals that teachers' professional training regarding learner diversity was rated at a high level (M = 4.00, SD = 0.32), indicating that it was often interpreted. Among the indicators, support for learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents received the highest score (M = 4.61, SD = 0.71), underscoring teachers' strong awareness of

inclusive education principles. Similarly, consideration of learners' linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds (M = 4.18, SD = 0.76) reflects educators' sensitivity to contextual factors influencing student learning. However, the inclusion of indigenous learners (M = 3.41, SD = 0.52) and assistance for learners in challenging circumstances (M = 3.63, SD = 0.62) received relatively lower ratings, indicating that, although teachers are trained in general inclusivity, they face challenges in addressing marginalized groups with unique learning needs. These disparities point to a need for more specialized training on culturally responsive pedagogy and social support systems for disadvantaged learners. This result highlights the growing importance of equity-driven practices in Philippine secondary schools as part of broader commitments to quality and inclusive education.

These results are supported by recent Philippine-based studies that examine the nuanced challenges of inclusive education for marginalized learners. (Pagaddut and Tamana, 2023) found that while teachers recognize the value of Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd), they underestimate the depth of cultural integration required, particularly in Social Studies instruction. Their findings suggest that educators often lack the pedagogical tools and reflective practices needed to fully embed indigenous knowledge systems into mainstream curricula. Similarly, (Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua, 2023) found that although teachers are aware of culturally responsive teaching (CRT), strategies such as contextualization and localization are underutilized, especially in classrooms with indigenous students. They emphasized the need for enhanced faculty development programs to support CRT implementation and prevent issues like discrimination and cultural disconnection.

Table 4
Level of Professional Training in Curriculum and Planning

Curriculum and Planning	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Design and use of assessment strategies	3.83	.51	Often
2. Monitoring and evaluation of learner progress	4.04	.84	Often
3. Providing feedback for learning improvement	3.94	.79	Often
4. Communicating learner progress to stakeholders	3.92	.81	Often
5. Using assessment data to enhance teaching practices	3.77	.68	Often
Mean Score	3.90	.41	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

In Table 4, the overall mean score of 3.90 (SD = 0.41) demonstrates that teachers often apply curriculum and planning competencies in their professional practice. The highest-rated area was monitoring and evaluation of learner progress (M = 4.04, SD = 0.84), suggesting that teachers regularly track student learning outcomes to inform instructional adjustments. Closely aligned with this is the provision of feedback for learning improvement (M = 3.94, SD = 0.79), which reflects teachers' commitment to formative assessment. Conversely, the lowest score was observed in the use of assessment data to enhance teaching practices (M = 3.77, SD = 0.68). This gap highlights that while assessment is widely practiced, translating assessment results into evidence-based teaching strategies remains a developmental area. The findings emphasize the need to strengthen teachers' data-driven decision-making skills to maximize the impact of assessment on instructional planning. In alignment with international education reforms, greater emphasis on assessment literacy and reflective use of data would enhance curriculum planning and elevate overall instructional quality.

Table 5
Level of Professional Training in Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Creating learning environments responsive to community needs	3.82	.76	Often
2. Engaging parents and the school community	4.30	.95	Always
3. Upholding professional ethics	4.92	.28	Always
4. Participating in professional networks	3.73	.89	Often
Mean Score	4.19	.39	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

As shown in Table 5, teachers rated their professional training in community linkages and professional engagement, with an overall mean of 4.19 (SD = 0.39), indicating they were often engaged. The highest indicator was upholding professional ethics (M = 4.92, SD = 0.28), which was consistently rated as *always*. This underscores teachers' firm adherence to ethical standards, reflecting a profound commitment to professionalism in their practice. Engagement with parents and the school community (M = 4.30, SD = 0.95) was also rated very highly, suggesting that collaboration beyond the classroom is recognized as a core aspect of teaching.

However, participation in professional networks (M = 3.73, SD = 0.89) was the lowest-rated aspect, pointing to limited involvement in broader professional communities. This

may be due to constraints such as time, resources, or access to networking opportunities. The results emphasize that while teachers are ethically grounded and community-oriented, institutional support should be enhanced to encourage broader professional collaborations. Strengthening these linkages will not only expand teachers' perspectives but also promote shared learning and innovation across educational settings. This finding is well-supported by recent studies highlighting the growing emphasis on community linkages and professional engagement in teacher development programs. (Quilapio and Callo, 2023) found that in-service training programs significantly enhanced teachers' competencies in community involvement, stakeholder collaboration, and professional growth. Santos (2024) further revealed that Filipino teachers perceive themselves as capable of demonstrating community engagement competencies, though they also identified areas for improvement that could guide future training needs. (Ecarma, 2024) emphasized the role of professional learning communities in empowering teachers, showing that collective engagement within school communities fosters both instructional quality and professional identity.

Table 6

Level of Professional Training in Personal Growth and Professional Development

Personal Growth and Professional Development	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Commitment to lifelong learning	4.61	.73	Always
2. Reflective practice for self-improvement	4.54	.77	Always
3. Engagement in professional development activities	4.55	.79	Always
4. Collaboration with colleagues for growth	2.76	.62	Rarely
5. Advocacy for teaching excellence	3.26	.52	Often
Mean Score	3.94	.45	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 6 shows that personal growth and professional development among teachers received an overall mean of 3.94 (SD = 0.45), which is interpreted as *often*. The highest ratings were given to commitment to lifelong learning (M = 4.61, SD = 0.73), reflective practice (M = 4.54, SD = 0.77), and engagement in professional development activities (M = 4.55, SD = 0.79), all of which were rated as *always*. These scores suggest that teachers consistently value self-improvement and professional advancement as central to their practice. In contrast, collaboration with colleagues for growth (M = 2.76, SD = 0.62) was rated *rarely*, signifying a notable gap in peer-to-peer professional development. Similarly, advocacy for teaching excellence (M = 3.26, SD = 0.52) was only rated *often*, reflecting a more moderate commitment. This disparity reveals that while teachers are individually motivated toward lifelong learning, collaborative practices and advocacies are

less emphasized. Encouraging collective engagement and fostering a culture of professional solidarity may therefore enhance overall growth and sustain innovation in schools.

The results that teachers “often” engage in personal growth and professional development are well-supported by recent literature emphasizing the evolving nature of teacher learning. (Padillo et al., 2021) found that Filipino educators consistently participate in professional development activities that enhance instructional planning, classroom management, and subject mastery. However, the perceived benefits vary depending on contextual factors. (Gepila, 2020) reinforced this by showing that teachers assessed themselves as “proficient” across multiple domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), particularly in managing learning environments and pursuing continuous improvement. In a broader international context, (Shurtleff, 2020) found that teachers value collaborative, goal-aligned professional development, though some express frustration when external mandates override their personal learning goals. Furthermore, Tables 8 to 10 show the level of school support available to teachers, measured across three domains: relational trust, mentorship, and adequate preparation. These dimensions are critical in determining the extent to which schools provide both relational and structural backing to teachers as they navigate curricular reforms. The results shed light on whether institutional support is sufficient and aligned with teachers’ professional needs.

Research Question 2: What is the level of school support as perceived by secondary teachers, specifically in terms of administrative support?

- d. Relational trust
- e. Mentorship
- f. Adequate Preparation

Table 7
Level of School Support in terms of Relational Trust

Relational trust	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Can speak to my administrative staff about classroom concerns.	2.37	1.03	Rarely
2. Can voice my concerns to my administrative staff without fear of repercussions.	2.80	1.01	Sometimes
3. Have conflict with another professional, I can speak to my administrative staff openly.	1.82	.82	Rarely
4. Has the administrative staff ever considered my concerns?	2.15	.75	Rarely
Mean Score	2.29	.48	Rarely

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

As indicated in Table 7, relational trust between teachers and administrative staff was low, with an overall mean of 2.29 (SD = 0.48), indicating it was rarely present. The ability to voice concerns without fear of repercussions (M = 2.80, SD = 1.01) was the most highly rated, though still within the *sometimes* category. In stark contrast, opportunities to openly discuss conflicts with administrators (M = 1.82, SD = 0.82) scored the lowest, highlighting a significant gap in transparent communication. These results point to an underlying climate of caution and mistrust, in which teachers feel hesitant to express their concerns fully. This lack of relational trust may affect morale and professional engagement, as open dialogue is a cornerstone of effective organizational culture. The findings suggest that administrative staff must actively work toward fostering trust, transparency, and open communication to strengthen collaboration and support among school stakeholders. Low levels of relational trust between teachers and administrative staff are consistently documented in recent research, especially in contexts marked by hierarchical decision-making, leadership turnover, and limited emotional safety. (Adams, 2020) found that while teachers generally trust their peers and principals, trust in district administration is significantly lower, averaging just 3.21 compared to 4.64 for principals—suggesting a disconnect in relational support from higher-level leadership. (Meek et al., 2020) examined trust during a leadership transition in a low-income school. They revealed that while teachers maintained strong collegial bonds, uncertainty and lack of shared vision with new administrators led to emotional discomfort and reduced instructional capacity. (Hong et al., 2020) emphasized that relational trust is built through vulnerability, shared goals, and emotional safety—elements often missing in administrative interactions, especially when leadership is unstable, or communication is top-down.

Table 8
Level of School Support in terms of Mentorship

Mentorship	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The administrative staff has encouraged me to collaborate with a more experienced teacher.	2.27	.74	Rarely
2. Has the administrative staff available when I have questions about curriculum or materials?	2.25	.63	Rarely
3. Has an administrative staff that values collaborative teaching and collaborative efforts	2.17	.99	Rarely
4. The administrative staff provides ongoing constructive feedback.	1.96	.80	Rarely

5. Has the administrative staff discouraged mentorship?	2.59	.69	Rarely
6. Has the administrative staff coached me when I need it?	2.10	.85	Rarely
7. Has the administrative staff acted as mentors?	2.73	.79	Sometimes
Mean Score	2.30	.35	Rarely

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 8 reveals that mentorship support from administrative staff was also rated low, with an overall mean of 2.30 (SD = 0.35), indicating it was rarely observed. Most indicators—such as providing constructive feedback (M = 1.96, SD = 0.80) and coaching when needed (M = 2.10, SD = 0.85) fell within the *rarely* range. The highest-rated item, in which administrative staff act as mentors (M = 2.73, SD = 0.79), reached only the 'sometimes' level. The findings indicate that teachers perceive mentorship as minimally practiced within their institutions—this lack of systematic mentoring limits opportunities for novice and experienced teachers alike to receive guided professional support. Without intentional mentorship structures, teachers may rely heavily on self-directed learning, potentially leading to uneven growth. Institutionalizing mentorship programs, therefore, emerges as a pressing need to ensure that professional growth is nurtured consistently and effectively across the teaching workforce.

Mentorship support from administrative staff was rated low. This is echoed in several recent studies that highlight systemic gaps in instructional mentoring and leadership engagement. (Overa, 2020) found that school heads in Zamboanga del Norte and Dipolog City demonstrated low levels of mentoring skill, which, while positively correlated with teacher performance, lacked consistency and depth across divisions. (Kutsyuruba, 2020) emphasized that administrator engagement is vital to effective teacher induction and mentoring programs, yet many administrators fail to provide sustained, structured support, especially for early-career teachers. (Samiano and Baluyos, 2022) further revealed that, while administrative support was perceived as high during modular distance learning, it did not significantly correlate with teacher performance, suggesting that mentorship, as a specific form of support, remains underdeveloped.

Table 9
Level of School Support in terms of Adequate Preparation

Adequate Preparation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Has the administrative staff taken time to create/acquire well-developed and informative professional development	3.56	.86	Often

2. Has the administrative staff equipped me with the necessary material for my classroom?	3.82	.68	Often
3. Has the administrative staff equipped me with the necessary curriculum for my classroom?	3.66	.89	Often
4. Has the administrative staff assisted with lesson planning and development?	2.87	.86	Sometimes
5. The administrative staff encourages me to continue learning.	3.00	.99	Sometimes
6. The administrative staff has discussions about my performance and provides areas of improvement.	3.00	.79	Sometimes
7. The administrative staff shares information about different learning opportunities outside of the school.	3.66	.84	Often
8. The administrative staff provides adequate planning time for me during the school day.	3.80	.95	Often
Mean Score	3.42	.42	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 9 presents a relatively higher evaluation of school support in terms of adequate preparation, with an overall mean of 3.42 (SD = 0.42), indicating that it is *often*. The strongest aspect was the provision of necessary classroom materials (M = 3.82, SD = 0.68), followed closely by adequate planning time during the school day (M = 3.80, SD = 0.95). These results suggest that schools make efforts to equip teachers with basic instructional resources and time for lesson planning. However, particular areas remain underdeveloped. Assistance with lesson planning (M = 2.87, SD = 0.86) and encouragement for continued learning (M = 3.00, SD = 0.99) received lower scores, both within the *sometimes* range. These findings suggest that while schools provide logistical and material support, professional encouragement and intellectual preparation are less emphasized. To further strengthen adequate preparation, schools must move beyond material provisions and foster a culture of pedagogical coaching and continuous encouragement. This would empower teachers not only to plan effectively but also to innovate and sustain long-term professional growth.

School support for teacher preparation was rated relatively high. This is well supported by recent studies that emphasize the role of institutional backing in enhancing instructional readiness. (Ronfeldt, 2021) highlighted that practice-based coursework and extended clinical experiences significantly improve teacher preparedness, especially

when schools provide structured mentoring and feedback systems. (Maramag et al., 2020) found that teacher education institutions (TEIs) with higher accreditation status and faculty qualifications tend to produce graduates who perform better on licensure examinations, suggesting that institutional support directly correlates with teacher readiness. (Burroughs et al., 2020) further emphasized that school-based resources—such as time allocated to planning, access to curriculum materials, and collaborative learning opportunities—are critical in shaping teachers’ opportunities to learn and apply effective practices. Proceeding with Tables 11 to 13, which present the level of success in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum as perceived by teachers, categorized into curriculum design and content, teaching and learning enhancement, and implementation and support. These results indicate how well the curriculum aligns with its intended objectives and the degree to which it is supported at the classroom and institutional levels.

Research Question 3: What is the level of success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation as observed by secondary teachers in terms of?

- d. Curriculum Design and Content
- e. Teaching and Learning Enhancement
- f. Implementation and Support

Table 10
Level of success in MATATAG Curriculum implementation: curriculum design and content

<i>Curriculum Design and Content</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. <i>Aligns with the national educational standards.</i>	4.42	.84	Always
2. <i>The learning objectives of the MATATAG curriculum are clear and attainable.</i>	4.25	.82	Always
3. <i>Promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills.</i>	4.00	1.16	Often
4. <i>Integrates academic, social, and emotional learning in a balanced manner.</i>	4.51	1.07	Always
5. <i>Encourages inclusivity and diversity.</i>	4.25	.77	Always
6. <i>Prepares students for real-life challenges through practical applications.</i>	4.39	.82	Always
7. <i>Does it have a digital literacy that is effectively integrated into the curriculum content?</i>	4.45	.97	Always
Mean Score	4.33	.39	Always

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = rarely, 2 = sometimes, 3 = often, 4 = always. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 11 shows that curriculum design and content were highly rated, with an overall mean of 4.33 (SD = 0.39), indicating they were consistently rated. The strongest indicator was the integration of academic, social, and emotional learning (M = 4.51, SD = 1.07), underscoring the MATATAG Curriculum's holistic orientation. Digital literacy integration (M = 4.45, SD = 0.97) and alignment with national educational standards (M = 4.42, SD = 0.84) were also rated as consistently practiced, indicating that teachers view the curriculum as both future-ready and compliant with national benchmarks. Although still positive, the promotion of critical thinking and problem-solving skills (M = 4.00, SD = 1.16) received the lowest mean. This suggests that while the curriculum is robust in design, its practical implementation of higher-order thinking may face contextual challenges, such as limited resources or pedagogical readiness. Overall, these findings affirm that the MATATAG Curriculum is perceived as comprehensive and forward-looking, yet further emphasis on critical and creative thinking would ensure its complete alignment with 21st-century learning goals.

Curriculum design and content were rated highly; this is interpreted as “always. This is strongly supported by recent literature emphasizing the centrality of well-structured curricula in effective teaching. (Filgona et al., 2020) underscore that teachers’ pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) is a critical driver of student achievement, especially when curriculum design integrates planning, implementation, and feedback mechanisms. (Dio, 2020) examined the Philippine K to 10 Mathematics curriculum and found that, despite some structural gaps, teachers generally perceived the vertical coherence and sequencing of content topics as strengths, contributing to instructional clarity and learner progression. (Carvajal et al., 2025) further emphasized that curriculum reforms aligned with Republic Act 10533 and the PPST have empowered teacher education institutions to deliver future-proof content, thereby reinforcing teachers’ confidence and competence in delivering the curriculum.

Table 11
Level of success in MATATAG Curriculum implementation: teaching and learning enhancement

Teaching and Learning Enhancement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Have teaching methods prescribed by the MATATAG curriculum enhanced student engagement?	4.44	.84	Always
2. Has collaborative learning been effectively facilitated through the curriculum?	4.38	.96	Always
3. The curriculum provides ample opportunities for experiential learning.	4.54	.65	Always

4. Allows for flexibility in teaching approaches to cater to different learning styles.	4.63	.54	Always
5. Innovative teaching methods are encouraged and supported by the curriculum.	4.66	.63	Always
6. Promotes a positive and supportive classroom environment.	4.41	1.27	Always
7. Provides clear guidelines for integrating technology into classroom instruction.	4.82	.49	Always
8. Includes ongoing support for teachers to address challenges in implementing it.	4.55	.94	Always
9. The school infrastructure supports the effective delivery of the MATATAG curriculum.	4.08	.95	Often
10. Ensures that professional development opportunities related to it are readily available.	3.63	1.21	Often
11. Fosters collaboration among teachers to enhance its implementation.	3.54	.79	Often
12. Is supported by adequate financial resources for all its aspects.	2.41	.87	Rarely
13. Ensures that technology resources are sufficient and accessible for both teachers and students.	3.03	.81	Sometimes
14. The implementation of the MATATAG curriculum has led to an improvement in students' academic performance.	4.48	.79	Always
15. Has positively impacted students' emotional and social well-being.	4.54	.77	Always
16. This has resulted in students showing increased resilience and adaptability.	4.45	.87	Always
17. Has fostered the development of stronger critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students.	4.14	.80	Often
18. Has provided evidence of improved student behavior and attitudes toward learning.	4.17	.81	Often

19. This has led to students exhibiting a greater awareness and understanding of environmental issues.	3.39	.90	Sometimes
Mean Score	4.12	.18	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 11 indicates that the teaching and learning enhancement dimension of the MATATAG Curriculum was rated favorably, with an overall mean of 4.12 (SD = 0.18), indicating that it was often rated. Notably, integrating technology into instruction received the highest rating (M = 4.82, SD = 0.49), affirming the curriculum’s responsiveness to digitalization in education. Flexibility in teaching approaches (M = 4.63, SD = 0.54) and innovative teaching methods (M = 4.66, SD = 0.63) were also consistently rated as *always*, reflecting adaptability to diverse learning styles. On the other hand, adequate financial resources (M = 2.41, SD = 0.87) and sufficient access to technology (M = 3.03, SD = 0.81) were rated significantly lower, indicating systemic constraints that hinder optimal implementation. While pedagogical aspects are well-supported, structural limitations in funding and resources create barriers to full-scale effectiveness. Thus, although the MATATAG Curriculum has positively influenced learner engagement, academic performance, and socio-emotional development, sustainable investment in infrastructure and resource allocation is necessary to ensure its consistent delivery across schools.

The favorable rating of the teaching and learning enhancement dimension of the MATATAG Curriculum is supported by emerging research that highlights its positive impact on instructional quality and learner engagement. (Abaiz et al., 2025) found that teachers appreciated the curriculum’s integration of core competencies and Filipino cultural values, noting improvements in foundational skills and mastery despite challenges in pacing and resource availability. (Balansag et al., 2024) further emphasized that the curriculum’s focus on humanized learning and reduced content overload led to improved student engagement and academic performance, particularly in subjects such as history and geography. Complementing these findings, policy reviews by (RISE Journals, 2024) revealed that the MATATAG Curriculum fosters a more conducive learning environment by streamlining teacher workload and enhancing instructional clarity.

Table 12

Level of success in MATATAG Curriculum implementation: Implementation and support

Implementation and Support	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Has contributed to students demonstrating increased cultural awareness and appreciation of diversity.	3.21	.92	Always

2. Employs a systematic approach to evaluating its effectiveness	3.99	.93	Often
3. Regularly seeks and utilizes student feedback to improve its implementation.	2.65	.91	Sometimes
4. Recognizes teacher feedback as crucial for its continuous improvement.	2.96	.98	Sometimes
5. Impact on student outcomes is regularly assessed and reported.	3.52	.73	Often
6. Is adjusted based on empirical evidence and feedback.	3.30	.82	Sometimes
7. Is committed to the ongoing improvement of the curriculum.	3.83	.91	Often
8. The effectiveness of professional development programs related to the curriculum is evaluated.	4.35	.63	Always
9. Encourages community and parental involvement in the evaluation process.	4.38	.66	Always
10. Implementation is reviewed to ensure alignment with educational trends and needs.	4.96	.20	Always
11. Establishes clear benchmarks and indicators for success in its implementation.	3.80	.79	Always
Mean Score	3.72	.30	Always

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

As presented in Table 12, implementation and support of the MATATAG Curriculum achieved an overall mean of 3.72 (SD = 0.30), indicating that it was often implemented and supported. The highest-rated aspect was the regular review of curriculum alignment with educational trends and needs (M = 4.96, SD = 0.20), highlighting the curriculum's adaptability to evolving contexts. Encouragement of parental and community involvement (M = 4.38, SD = 0.66) and evaluation of professional development programs (M = 4.35, SD = 0.63) were also highly valued, suggesting a strong emphasis on collaborative and evidence-based implementation. However, student feedback utilization (M = 2.65, SD = 0.91) and teacher feedback recognition (M = 2.96, SD = 0.98) were rated only *sometimes*, revealing a gap in participatory evaluation. This indicates that while systemic mechanisms are in place, grassroots-level feedback integration is less of a priority. Such a gap risks reducing teacher and student agency in shaping curriculum outcomes. These findings

underscore the importance of democratizing curriculum implementation by amplifying classroom voices.

The implementation and support of the MATATAG Curriculum were rated “often. This is well supported by recent Philippine studies that examine both the strengths and challenges of this reform initiative. (Villaver, 2024) conducted an integrative literature review and found that while teachers generally perceive the curriculum as relevant and aligned with national education goals, its success depends heavily on sustained support systems such as professional development, inclusive practices, and monitoring mechanisms. (Malinao and Miano, 2025) revealed that teachers actively adapt through peer collaboration and resource improvisation. However, they still face barriers, including insufficient training, limited infrastructure, and an administrative workload, that hinder their ability to implement the curriculum fully. (Po, 2025) further emphasized that school heads and teachers face implementation challenges that directly affect student performance, especially in Grade 7, underscoring the need for stronger institutional support and curriculum adaptation strategies. Henceforth, with all the discussions above, Tables 13 to 15 summarize the overall results across the three significant variables: professional training, school support, and success in curriculum implementation. These consolidated results provide a comparative view of each variable's relative strengths and weaknesses, offering a clearer perspective on teachers' and schools' readiness for curricular reform.

Research Question 4: Is there a significant relationship between professional training as a predictor of the success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation?

Table 13
Summary of Professional Training Among Secondary School Teachers

Professionals Training Domains	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.82	.42	Often
Learning Environment	4.07	.26	Often
Diversity of Learners	4.00	.32	Often
Curriculum and Planning	3.90	.41	Often
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	4.19	.39	Often
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.84	.45	Often
Overall Mean Score	3.97	.19	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = rarely, 2 = sometimes, 3 = often, 4 = always. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 13 presents a consolidated view of professional training across six domains, yielding an overall mean of 3.97 (SD = 0.19), interpreted as *often*. Among the domains,

community linkages and professional engagement ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 0.39$) emerged as the highest, reflecting teachers' strong ethical commitment and involvement with stakeholders beyond the classroom. Conversely, content knowledge and pedagogy ($M = 3.82$, $SD = 0.42$) registered the lowest scores, suggesting that, while teachers are competent, continuous upgrading of pedagogical approaches remains necessary. The summary highlights that teachers demonstrate consistent professional competence across domains, though the variation in scores suggests uneven development. This indicates that institutional training initiatives should prioritize bolstering instructional practices while sustaining teachers' strengths in community engagement and professional ethics. Collectively, the data portray teachers as capable practitioners who, with sustained support, can further elevate instructional quality and learner outcomes.

The observed consistency in teacher competence across domains, coupled with uneven development, aligns with (Jentsch and König's, 2022) assertion that teacher competence is multidimensional and evolves differently across cognitive, affective, and instructional facets. (Popova et al., 2022) further emphasize that professional development programs often fail to address these disparities because the training content is poorly aligned with actual classroom needs, especially in instructional practice. Locally, (Herrera, 2024) found that Filipino teachers exhibit strong ethical and community-engagement capacities but require targeted support in instructional strategies and assessment design, as revealed by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) framework.

Table 14

Summary of School Support Among Secondary School Teachers

School Support Domains	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
Relational trust	2.29	.48	Rarely
Mentorship	2.30	.35	Rarely
Adequate Preparation	3.42	.42	Often
Overall Mean Score	2.67	.21	Rarely

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

As shown in Table 14, the overall mean score for school support was 2.67 ($SD = 0.21$), interpreted as *rarely*. Among the domains, adequate preparation received the highest rating ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.42$), suggesting that schools provide at least some logistical and material assistance. However, relational trust ($M = 2.29$, $SD = 0.48$) and mentorship ($M = 2.30$, $SD = 0.35$) were consistently rated low, reflecting a lack of supportive professional relationships and structured mentoring within schools. This pattern reveals a concerning imbalance: while administrative support extends to materials and preparation, relational and professional support structures remain underdeveloped. Such limitations may hinder teachers' sense of belonging and professional growth. The findings call for deliberate

reforms in school leadership practices, with emphasis on building trust, fostering mentorship, and creating environments where teachers feel valued and supported beyond material provisions.

The imbalance between logistical support and relational-professional structures in schools is well documented in the educational literature. (Edwards-Groves et al., 2016) emphasize that relational trust is foundational to school-based improvement efforts, particularly when middle leaders facilitate professional dialogue and collaborative inquiry. (Kolleck et al., 2021) further demonstrate that trust among teachers is not automatically fostered through collaboration alone; it requires intentional structures that promote reciprocity, shared values, and sustained interaction². Meanwhile, (Mori, 2023) highlights the transformative role of mentorship in cultivating teacher leadership and enhancing school culture, arguing that structured mentoring relationships empower teachers to grow professionally and contribute meaningfully to institutional development.

Table 15
Summary of Success in the Implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum in Secondary School Teachers

Success of Implementation Domains	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
Curriculum Design and Content	4.33	.39	Always
Teaching and Learning Enhancement	4.12	.18	Often
Implementation and Support	3.72	.30	Often
Overall Mean Score	4.06	.19	Often

Note. Responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = *rarely*, 2 = *sometimes*, 3 = *often*, 4 = *always*. Higher mean scores indicate more favorable evaluations.

Table 15 synthesizes the success of the MATATAG Curriculum’s implementation, yielding an overall mean score of 4.06 (SD = 0.19), which is often interpreted. Curriculum design and content were rated highest (M = 4.33, SD = 0.39), affirming the curriculum’s strength in structure and alignment with standards. Teaching and learning enhancement (M = 4.12, SD = 0.18) was also rated positively, suggesting effective integration of innovative pedagogical strategies. In comparison, implementation and support (M = 3.72, SD = 0.30) received the lowest rating, indicating that systemic and logistical supports lag behind curricular design. These results imply that while the MATATAG Curriculum is conceptually strong and pedagogically enriching, its sustainability depends on the robustness of implementation mechanisms. Adequate resourcing, teacher feedback systems, and participatory evaluation must be strengthened to ensure that curriculum reforms are not only theoretically sound but also practically sustained across diverse school contexts.

The MATATAG Curriculum’s conceptual strength and pedagogical promise echo global findings on curriculum reform, where design excellence often outpaces implementation capacity. (Chimbunde and Moreeng, 2024) argue that the sustainability of curriculum reform hinges on active teacher participation throughout the design and rollout phases, which fosters ownership and fidelity in implementation. (Peng et al., 2025) reinforce this

by showing that curriculum leadership and stakeholder engagement are critical to translating curricular vision into sustainable school practices. Meanwhile, (Ali, 2024) highlights that logistical support, interdisciplinary integration, and feedback mechanisms are essential for embedding sustainability into modern curricula, especially in contexts where systemic challenges persist. Lastly, the discussion is whether there is a significant relationship between professional training and the success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation. Table 17 elaborates on the correlation between professional training and success in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum, and Table 18 tests the significant relationship between School Support among secondary school teachers and the level of success in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Research Question 5. Is there a significant relationship between school support as a predictor of the success of the MATATAG curriculum implementation?

Table 16
Correlation between professional training and success in the MATATAG Curriculum implementation

<i>Professional Training Domains</i>	R	P-value	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.178	.137	Not Significant
Learning Environment	-.095	.431	Not Significant
Diversity of Learners	.336 **	.004	Significant
Curriculum and Planning	.063	.600	Not Significant
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	.115	.340	Not Significant
Personal Growth and Professional Development	.227	.056	Not Significant
Overall Mean Score	.288 *	.015	Significant
Note. Correlation values are based on Pearson's r. $p < .05$ is significant (*); $p < .01$ is highly significant (**). Positive coefficients indicate that higher levels of professional training are associated with greater success in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.			

Table 16 shows that professional training is statistically significantly associated with curriculum implementation across specific domains. Specifically, learner diversity ($r = .336$, $p = .004$) showed a significant positive correlation, underscoring the critical role of inclusive education practices in ensuring successful curriculum implementation. Additionally, the overall mean score of professional training was significantly related to implementation success ($r = .288$, $p = .015$), suggesting that higher levels of professional competence generally enhance curriculum delivery. Other domains, such as content knowledge and pedagogy ($r = .178$, $p = .137$) and learning environment ($r = -.095$, $p = .431$), did not demonstrate significant relationships. This indicates that while

foundational teaching competencies are necessary, their direct link to curriculum success may be less immediate than that of inclusivity-focused training. This means the null hypothesis was rejected for these two variables but retained for the other domains.

The result highlights an important insight: while certain domains alone may not strongly predict curriculum success, the overall mean score does. This occurs because averaging across domains reduces variability and measurement error, allowing the combined effect of multiple training competencies to emerge more clearly. In other words, teachers' professional training works synergistically—no single dimension is decisive; together, they significantly enhance teachers' capacity to implement curricular reforms. The substantial contribution of learners' diverse domains further underscores the importance of inclusivity as a key driver of curriculum success. Hence, the null hypothesis H_01 is rejected. The findings are strongly supported by recent literature that explores the nuanced relationship between professional training and curriculum implementation, particularly in the context of inclusive education. (Holmqvist and Lelinge, 2020) conducted a systematic review. They found that collaborative professional development significantly enhances teachers' attitudes and practices toward inclusion, aligning with your result that diversity of learners is a key domain where training impacts implementation. (Ackah-Jnr, 2020) emphasized that in-service professional development fosters teacher efficacy and preparedness for inclusive education, especially when training is embedded in both formal and informal learning contexts—mirroring your finding that overall professional competence contributes to curriculum success. (Jimenez, 2025), in a Philippine-based study, found that although inclusive education implementation is generally high, challenges persist due to inconsistent training and infrastructure gaps, suggesting that foundational competencies, such as content knowledge and pedagogy, may not directly translate into successful implementation.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn from the findings of the study:

Professional training across six domains yields an overall mean of 3.97 (SD = 0.19), indicating that it is often. Among the domains, community linkages and professional engagement (M = 4.19, SD = 0.39) emerged as the highest, reflecting teachers' strong ethical commitment and involvement with stakeholders beyond the classroom. Conversely, content knowledge and pedagogy (M = 3.82, SD = 0.42) registered the lowest scores, suggesting that, while teachers are competent, continuous upgrading of pedagogical approaches remains necessary. School support yields an overall mean of 2.67 (SD = 0.21), interpreted as *rarely*. Among the domains, adequate preparation received the highest rating (M = 3.42, SD = 0.42), suggesting that schools provide at least some logistical and material assistance. However, relational trust (M = 2.29, SD = 0.48) and mentorship (M = 2.30, SD = 0.35) were consistently rated low, reflecting a lack of supportive professional relationships and structured mentoring within schools.

The implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum yields an overall mean score of 4.06 (SD = 0.19), which is often interpreted as indicating success. Curriculum design and

content were rated highest ($M = 4.33$, $SD = 0.39$), affirming the curriculum's strength in structure and alignment with standards. Teaching and learning enhancement ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.18$) was also rated positively, suggesting effective integration of innovative pedagogical strategies. In comparison, implementation and support ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.30$) received the lowest rating, indicating that systemic and logistical supports lag behind curricular design. Professional training is statistically significantly related to curriculum implementation in specific domains. Specifically, learner diversity ($r = .336$, $p = .004$) showed a significant positive correlation, underscoring the critical role of inclusive education practices in ensuring successful curriculum implementation. Thus, this means the null hypothesis was rejected for these two variables but retained for the other domains. None of the domains of school support were significantly correlated with the success of the MATATAG Curriculum implementation. For instance, relational trust ($r = -.211$, $p = .077$) and mentorship ($r = .083$, $p = .494$) were both non-significant, while adequate preparation ($r = .016$, $p = .894$) also lacked statistical impact. The overall mean score ($r = -.97$, $p = .419$) further confirms the absence of significant associations. Thus, the null Hypothesis H_0 is not rejected.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are based on the study's findings:

Department of Education Policymakers. The need to prioritize sustained, domain-specific professional development programs, especially those that enhance teachers' capacity to address learner diversity and apply inclusive pedagogical strategies. Given the lack of significant correlation between school support and curriculum implementation, policy reforms should shift focus from material provisions to relational and developmental structures—such as mentoring frameworks and trust-building initiatives. Embed participatory evaluation mechanisms to ensure that curriculum reforms like the MATATAG Curriculum are responsive to classroom realities and teacher feedback.

School Leaders and Administrators. Recalibrate school support systems to go beyond logistical assistance by cultivating a culture of relational trust and structured mentorship. While adequate preparation is moderately present, its limited impact on curriculum success suggests that leadership must invest in professional relationships and collaborative planning. Empower teacher leaders to co-design support initiatives, ensuring that administrative efforts align with the pedagogical demands of inclusive and differentiated instruction.

Secondary Educators. Engage actively in professional development opportunities that strengthen competencies in inclusive education, reflective practice, and curriculum planning. The significant link between training and implementation success—particularly in addressing learner diversity—highlights the value of continuous learning and pedagogical adaptability. Advocate for mentoring and peer collaboration within your schools to foster a supportive environment that complements individual growth. Researchers. Further investigate the nuanced dynamics among professional training, school support, and curriculum implementation, particularly across diverse school

contexts and teacher profiles. The non-significant findings on school support warrant deeper qualitative exploration to uncover latent factors that may influence teacher performance. Develop validated instruments that capture relational and structural dimensions of support, and contribute to evidence-based models for inclusive curriculum delivery.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research, titled “Professional Training and School Support as Predictors in the Implementation of MATATAG Curriculum”, is anchored on System Theory by Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1998), and was conducted in full adherence to ethical principles governing educational research, aligned with the 2017 National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research (adapted for social and educational studies), the Declaration of Helsinki and policies of the researcher’s academic institution. Before data collection, formal permission to conduct the study was requested and granted by the Department of Education, Division of Bukidnon, San Fernando District 1, with additional endorsement from the participating schools’ administrations. All participants (school head, teachers and curriculum coordinators) were informed of the study’s purpose, procedures and alignment with System Theory’s focus on interconnected components of the educational systems. Voluntary participation was emphasized with the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. The researcher declares no conflicts of interest and confirms that this work is original, properly cited, and has not been submitted to any other institution.

Acknowledgments

She wants to thank everyone who helped with the effort detailed in this thesis. First and foremost, she is grateful to the all-powerful God who has given her the courage and discernment to pursue graduate school. Secondly, she would like to thank her academic advisor, Dr. Phoebe Aguilar. She encouraged me to study, exposed me to new ideas, held me to a high quality of work in all she did, and let me be creative with my work, all of which contributed to my successful graduate school experience. She wanted to thank her family and friends for their support while she was here. The first and greatest person she wants to thank is her beloved husband, Danelson V. Collado. His constant assistance, tolerance, and comprehension have been invaluable, particularly throughout the most trying times of her thesis. She will always be thankful for his support, readiness to hear my difficulties, and unshakable faith in her skills. The accomplishment is equally ours, and she dedicates her thesis to him with all her love and gratitude. Franzhane Kizhia Zuniga y Dan Travis Z. Collado. Zuniga’s love, support, and encouragement propelled her scholastic career. They have motivated her to keep going when things become tough, and having you here has added even more significance to my achievement. She loves you more than words express, and will always appreciate your understanding and patience. She is grateful to her parents, Miralona and Edison G. Zuniga, for their unfailing love, support, and encouragement during her academic career, especially during the arduous process of finishing this thesis. They have been important in their unwavering faith in her abilities, willingness to listen, and persistent belief in her. This accomplishment would not have been feasible without your steadfast love and emotional support. She

appreciates everything. She sincerely thanks her sibling, Elorah Dawn M. Zuniga, for their unfailing encouragement and support during this journey. Even at the worst moments, their understanding was invaluable to her. She could not have completed this thesis without their love and faith in her. Lastly, she is also incredibly appreciative of her friends' steadfast support and for helping to make this path easier. Thank you very much!

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